

Testing Consecutive Epochs of Cosmic Expansion against Type Ia Supernovae Observations as a Phenomenological Alternative to Explain the Observed Curvature in the Hubble Diagram

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ABSTRACT

A paradigm shift that revolutionised cosmology and established mysterious dark energy as a dominant component of the Universe unveiled through the startling discovery of cosmic acceleration from type Ia supernovae (SNe Ia) observations. Here, I present and test a phenomenological alternative in which the observed curvature in the SNe Ia Hubble diagram, attributed to cosmic acceleration, arises as a result of consecutive epochs of cosmic expansion, wherein one expansion epoch of the Universe is consecutively followed by the next. Overlaying the predicted distances for consecutively-expanding particles (particles entering the Hubble flow consecutively – one particle after another) and the Λ CDM predictions on the Pantheon+ SNe Ia Hubble diagram, I find that the proposed model tracks the observed curvature of the Pantheon+ SNe Ia Hubble diagram over the tested redshift range, suggesting that consecutive expansion epochs may provide a viable alternative explanation why distant or high-redshift SNe Ia are further away than expected.

Keywords: Observational cosmology – Type Ia supernovae – Cosmological models – Expanding Universe – Accelerating Universe – Dark energy

1. INTRODUCTION

The startling and serendipitous discovery of cosmic acceleration inferred from SNe Ia observations (Riess et al. 1998; Perlmutter et al. 1999) continues to remain one of the most bewildering and significant discoveries in cosmology. The comparison of the distance-redshift relation for high- and low-redshift supernovae (SNe) revealed that high-redshift SNe are significantly dimmer, as they are further away than expected. Additional studies (Amanullah et al. 2010; Suzuki et al. 2012; Betoule et al. 2014; Demianski et al. 2017; Dirirsa et al. 2019; Brout et al. 2022; Scolnic et al. 2022) have also demonstrated this extraordinary feat with an undisputed streak of precision.

In the standard Λ CDM (Lambda Cold Dark Matter) framework, this dimness or the further-away-than-expected placement of high-redshift objects is explained by invoking dark energy – a hypothetical energy component responsible for transitioning the Universe’s expansion from past deceleration at high redshifts to recent acceleration at low redshifts. While compelling, this inference relies on the assumption that all observed objects participate in a single, continuous expansion (“cosmic deceleration that preceded the current epoch of cosmic acceleration” (Riess et al. 2004)).

However, an alternative interpretation, inspired by the above description provided by Riess et al. (2004), is possible through multiple, consecutive expansions (“consecutive expansion epochs that preceded the current epoch of cosmic expansion”). In this view, different objects entered the Hubble flow consecutively, or at different cosmic times, or in different expansion epochs. When these separate, consecutive expansion epochs are observed and plotted together, they produce the curvature in the Hubble diagram.

2. METHODOLOGY

It is valuable, according to Riess et al. (2004), to consider the distance-redshift relation of SNe Ia as a purely *kinematic* record of the expansion history of the Universe, without regard to its cause. Following Riess et al. (2004), a purely *kinematic* (i.e., cause-independent) description is also adopted here for the construction of a phenomenological model of consecutively-expanding particles. Here, the particles enter the Hubble flow consecutively (one particle after another) in descending order of their redshifts; the purpose of such a construction is to help model an expansion based on observations along our past light cone; the model implies that objects observed at high redshifts entered the Hubble flow earlier as compared to objects observed at low redshifts. Now, whether this construction makes us occupy a privileged position in an inhomogeneous Universe (Vishniac 2021, private communication) or puts us at the centre of an isotropic but inhomogeneous model (Davis 2022, private communication) is a question left open for further discussion.

33 particles were obtained with uniformly-spaced redshifts ($0.01 \leq z \leq 0.97$ ($\Delta z = 0.03$)) and uniformly-spaced expansion epochs (3.80×10^{17} seconds $\leq t_E \leq 7.00 \times 10^{17}$ seconds ($\Delta t = 10^{16}$ seconds)) to span the observed redshift range of 1564 SNe Ia ($0.01017 \leq z \leq 0.97423$); here, each particle represents an epoch of cosmic expansion. High-redshift particle ($z = 0.97$) entered the Hubble flow earlier in the preceding epoch of cosmic expansion (7.00×10^{17} seconds ago) as compared to its low-redshift counterpart ($z = 0.01$) that entered the Hubble flow comparatively later in the current (or more recent) epoch of cosmic expansion (3.80×10^{17} seconds ago).

The resultant Hubble diagram for these 33 consecutively-expanding particles was overlaid on the Hubble diagram for the most comprehensive SNe Ia compilation to date – the Pantheon+ (Brout et al. 2022; Scolnic et al. 2022) (Figure 1). Subsequently, these 33 consecutively-expanding particles ($0.01 \leq z \leq 0.97$) were evaluated, using RMSE (root mean square error (error metric)) and R^2 (coefficient of determination (goodness-of-fit metric)) as the evaluation metrics, against 1564 Pantheon+ SNe Ia ($0.01017 \leq z \leq 0.97423$) through nearest-neighbour interpolation (Figure 2A) and PCHIP (Piecewise Cubic Hermite Interpolating Polynomial) interpolation (Figure 2B).

The proposed phenomenological model was further tested using a different set of 66 particles ($0.011044 \leq z \leq 0.970439$) obtained by binning 1569 Pantheon+ SNe Ia ($0.01017 \leq z \leq 1.04817$) to span the observed redshift range of 1564 Pantheon+ SNe Ia ($0.01017 \leq z \leq 0.97423$). The purpose of this binning is to obtain the expansion onset time (t_E) for a given epoch, or the time when particles entered the Hubble flow (Equation (7) or Equation (9)), these Hubble flow onset timings (t_E) were eventually used to reconstruct the luminosity distances (Equation (5)) for these 66 particles ($0.011044 \leq z \leq 0.970439$); to be more precise, this binning has been deployed as a probe to help delineate different epochs of cosmic expansion (or expansion in different epochs) with high fidelity. The resultant Hubble diagram for this 66-particle model was overlaid on the Hubble diagram for 1564 Pantheon+ SNe Ia ($0.01017 \leq z \leq 0.97423$). Subsequently, the model was evaluated (RMSE and R^2) against the Pantheon+ SNe data through PCHIP interpolation (Figure 3, right panel).

For reference, Λ CDM predictions using *CosmoCalc* (Wright 2006) for 1564 Pantheon+ SNe Ia ($0.01017 \leq z \leq 0.97423$) using the Pantheon+ best-fit cosmology ($H_0 = 73.5$ km s⁻¹ Mpc⁻¹, $\Omega_M = 0.334$, $\Omega_\Lambda = 0.666$) were also overlaid on the Pantheon+ SNe Ia Hubble diagram and evaluated (RMSE and R^2) against the Pantheon+ SNe data (Figure 3, left panel).

3. DEFINING LUMINOSITY DISTANCES FOR COMPARISON

Distance measurements for SNe Ia are described as luminosity distances (D_L), and are defined from the inverse-square law (Schmidt 2012) as the ratio of intrinsic luminosity (L), to the observed flux (F) (Schmidt et al. 1998) as,

$$D_L = \sqrt{\frac{L}{4\pi F}} \quad (1)$$

If the luminosity distance (D_L) is in units of megaparsecs (Mpc) (Riess et al. 1998), then the distance modulus (μ) is,

$$\mu = 5 \log (D_L) + 25 \quad (2)$$

Rearranging Equation (1) or solving for flux (F) gives,

$$F = \frac{L}{4\pi D_L^2} \quad (3)$$

The low-redshift luminosity distance (D_L) relation for SNe Ia is,

$$D_L = \frac{cz}{H_0} \quad (4)$$

where c is the speed of light, z is the redshift, and H_0 is the Hubble parameter or the current expansion rate of the Universe.

Using Equation (4), I define for the proposed model a phenomenological luminosity distance (D_L) for comparison against SNe Ia luminosity distances as,

$$D_L = \frac{cz}{H} \quad (5)$$

Here, H is the phenomenological expansion rate for a given epoch. Just as the inverse of H_0 yields the Hubble time (t_H), the inverse of this phenomenological expansion rate (H), within the framework of this proposed model, yields the expansion onset time (t_E) for a given epoch, or the time when particles entered the Hubble flow as,

$$\frac{1}{H} = t_E \quad (6)$$

Equation (5) can be written for the proposed model so that it contains the expansion onset time (t_E) term as,

$$D_L = cz t_E \quad (7)$$

From the phenomenological luminosity distance defined in Equation (7) for the proposed model, Equation (1) defined for SNe Ia luminosity distances can be written for the proposed model as,

$$cz t_E = \sqrt{\frac{L}{4\pi F}} \quad (8)$$

And, in terms of t_E as,

$$t_E = \frac{1}{cz} \sqrt{\frac{L}{4\pi F}} \quad (9)$$

Rearranging Equation (8) or solving for flux (F) gives,

$$F = \frac{L}{4\pi (cz t_E)^2} \quad (10)$$

In the standard cosmological scenario, it is the presence of dark energy, driving cosmic acceleration, that causes D_L to increase, as a result, high-redshift SNe Ia appear dimmer (Equation (3)). For the proposed model, it is the presence of t_E that causes D_L to increase as per consecutive epochs of cosmic expansion, wherein objects observed at high redshifts entered the Hubble flow earlier (in the preceding epochs of cosmic expansion) as compared to objects observed at low redshifts, as a result, high-redshift objects appear dimmer (Equation (10)).

As a test, the luminosity distance (D_L) for the high-redshift SN Ia (Candidate ID: *Omba*) from the Pantheon+ SNe Ia compilation, having a distance modulus (μ) of 44.1111 and a redshift (z) of 0.97423, is 6640.793871 Mpc. Using Equation (3) defined for SNe Ia, the flux (F) received from it can be calculated, assuming that SNe Ia peak at 4×10^9 solar luminosities (L_\odot) (Riess 2012) or 1.5312×10^{36} W (where $1 L_\odot = 3.828 \times 10^{26}$ W (International Astronomical Union)), as 2.9018×10^{-18} W m⁻². Now, as per the proposed model, if t_E (the Hubble flow onset time) for the galaxy hosting this particular SN Ia (*Omba*) is 7.0111772×10^{17} seconds, then the same value of flux (F) is obtained for this SN using Equation (10) defined for the proposed model. In other words, with the corresponding value of H in Equation (5), or with the corresponding value of t_E in Equation (7), SNe Ia luminosity distances can be reconstructed.

4. RESULTS

The overlay of the Hubble diagram for 33 consecutively-expanding particles ($0.01 \leq z \leq 0.97$) on the Hubble diagram for 1564 Pantheon+ SNe Ia ($0.01017 \leq z \leq 0.97423$), depicted in [Figure 1](#), shows that the proposed model tracks the observed curvature of the Pantheon+ SNe Ia Hubble diagram.

Figure 1. Hubble diagram for 33 consecutively-expanding particles ($0.01 \leq z \leq 0.97$) overlaid on the Hubble diagram for 1564 Pantheon+ SNe Ia ($0.01017 \leq z \leq 0.97423$).

The evaluation of this 33-particle model against the Pantheon+ SNe data through nearest-neighbour interpolation ([Figure 2A](#)) yields RMSE and R^2 of 0.2011 and 0.9959, respectively (full sample of 33 data points) ([Figure 2A](#), left panel), and, RMSE of 0.0585 (15 low-residual data points ($|\Delta\mu| \leq 0.1$) from nearest-neighbour interpolation), still spanning the entire redshift range ([Figure 2A](#), right panel), whereas PCHIP interpolation ([Figure 2B](#)) yields RMSE and R^2 of 0.3119 and 0.9971, respectively (full sample of 1564 PCHIP-interpolated data points) ([Figure 2B](#), left panel), and, RMSE of 0.0576 (355 low-residual data points ($|\Delta\mu| < 0.1$) from PCHIP interpolation), still spanning the entire redshift range ([Figure 2B](#), right panel), suggesting that the observed SNe Ia data points can be partitioned into distinct groups consistent with, (i) objects entering the Hubble flow in different epochs of cosmic expansion (to explain the observed scatter of SNe Ia data points on the Hubble diagram), and, (ii) consecutive epochs of cosmic expansion – objects entering the Hubble flow consecutively (one after another) – implying that objects observed at high redshifts entered the Hubble flow earlier as compared to objects observed at low redshifts (to explain the observed further-away-than-expected placement of SNe Ia data points on the Hubble diagram).

Figure 2A. Hubble diagram for 33 consecutively-expanding particles ($0.01 \leq z \leq 0.97$) overlaid on the Hubble diagram for 33 Pantheon+ SNe Ia ($0.01017 \leq z \leq 0.97423$) for comparison through nearest-neighbour interpolation (left panel). The 15 low-residual data points ($|\Delta\mu| \leq 0.1$), from nearest-neighbour interpolation, still spanning the entire redshift range, suggest that the model does have regions that capture observations with high fidelity (right panel).

Figure 2B. Hubble diagram for 33 consecutively-expanding particles ($0.01 \leq z \leq 0.97$) overlaid on the Hubble diagram for 1564 Pantheon+ SNe Ia ($0.01017 \leq z \leq 0.97423$) for comparison through PCHIP interpolation (left panel). The 355 low-residual data points ($|\Delta\mu| < 0.1$), from PCHIP interpolation, still spanning the entire redshift range, suggest that the model does have regions that capture observations with high fidelity (right panel).

The expansion rate (H) (phenomenologically defined using Equation (5)) derived from the most distant, high-redshift particle ($z = 0.97$) that entered the Hubble flow earlier in the preceding epoch of cosmic expansion is $44.0814 \text{ km s}^{-1} \text{ Mpc}^{-1}$; significantly lower than an expansion rate of $81.2026 \text{ km s}^{-1} \text{ Mpc}^{-1}$ derived from the very nearby, low-redshift particle ($z = 0.01$) that entered the Hubble flow comparatively later in the current (or more recent) epoch of cosmic expansion, moreover, the inverse of these particle-derived expansion rates (Equation (6)) directly yields the expansion onset time (t_E) for a given epoch, allowing exact epoch timing to be estimated, or when the particles entered the Hubble flow.

The overlay of the Hubble diagram for the 66-particle model ($0.011044 \leq z \leq 0.970439$) on the Hubble diagram for 1564 Pantheon+ SNe Ia ($0.01017 \leq z \leq 0.97423$), depicted in Figure 3 (right panel), shows that the proposed model, based on binned SNe Ia data points, tracks the observed curvature of the Pantheon+ SNe Ia Hubble diagram and delineates different epochs of cosmic expansion (or expansion in different epochs) with high fidelity, as anticipated.

Figure 3. Λ CDM predictions for 1564 Pantheon+ SNe Ia ($0.01017 \leq z \leq 0.97423$) using the Pantheon+ best-fit cosmology ($H_0 = 73.5 \text{ km s}^{-1} \text{ Mpc}^{-1}$, $\Omega_M = 0.334$, $\Omega_\Lambda = 0.666$) overlaid on the Hubble diagram for 1564 Pantheon+ SNe Ia ($0.01017 \leq z \leq 0.97423$) for comparison against the Pantheon+ SNe data (left panel). The 66-particle model ($0.011044 \leq z \leq 0.970439$) also overlaid on the Hubble diagram for 1564 Pantheon+ SNe Ia ($0.01017 \leq z \leq 0.97423$) for comparison against the Pantheon+ SNe data through PCHIP interpolation (right panel).

Based on the Hubble flow onset timings (t_E) obtained from the binned data (Equation (7)), 66 particles are consistent with having entered the Hubble flow in different epochs of cosmic expansion; out of these 66 particles, 30 particles ($0.013227 \leq z \leq 0.970439$) are consistent with having entered the Hubble flow consecutively (one particle after another). High-redshift particle ($z = 0.970439$) entered the Hubble flow earlier in the preceding epoch of cosmic expansion (6.6145086×10^{17} seconds ago) as compared to a low-redshift particle ($z = 0.013227$) that entered the Hubble flow comparatively later in the current (or more recent) epoch of cosmic expansion (4.2797250×10^{17} seconds ago).

The evaluation of this 66-particle model against the Pantheon+ SNe data through PCHIP interpolation yields RMSE and R^2 of 0.1481 and 0.9974, respectively (full sample of 1564 PCHIP-interpolated data points) (Figure 3, right panel), suggesting that the observed SNe Ia data points can be partitioned into distinct groups consistent with, (i) objects entering

the Hubble flow in different epochs of cosmic expansion (to explain the observed scatter of SNe Ia data points on the Hubble diagram), and, (ii) consecutive epochs of cosmic expansion – objects entering the Hubble flow consecutively (one after another) – implying that objects observed at high redshifts entered the Hubble flow earlier as compared to objects observed at low redshifts (to explain the observed further-away-than-expected placement of SNe Ia data points on the Hubble diagram).

For reference, Λ CDM predictions using *CosmoCalc* (Wright 2006) for 1564 Pantheon+ SNe Ia ($0.01017 \leq z \leq 0.97423$) using the Pantheon+ best-fit cosmology ($H_0 = 73.5 \text{ km s}^{-1} \text{ Mpc}^{-1}$, $\Omega_M = 0.334$, $\Omega_\Lambda = 0.666$) evaluated against the Pantheon+ SNe Ia data ($0.01017 \leq z \leq 0.97423$) yields RMSE and R^2 of 0.1527 and 0.9973, respectively (Figure 3, left panel).

Since 66 particles ($0.011044 \leq z \leq 0.970439$) were obtained by binning 1569 Pantheon+ SNe Ia ($0.01017 \leq z \leq 1.04817$) to span the observed redshift range of 1564 Pantheon+ SNe Ia ($0.01017 \leq z \leq 0.97423$), therefore, the 66-particle model performs comparatively better; however, this better performance of the proposed model through binning should be viewed as an attempt to help accurately trace different epochs of cosmic expansion (or expansion in different epochs) on the SNe Ia Hubble diagram, rather than as an attempt to outperform the Λ CDM model.

For the 66-particle model also, the expansion rate (H) (phenomenologically defined using Equation (5)) derived from the most distant, high-redshift particle ($z = 0.970439$) that entered the Hubble flow earlier in the preceding epoch of cosmic expansion is $46.6504 \text{ km s}^{-1} \text{ Mpc}^{-1}$; significantly lower than an expansion rate of $72.1004 \text{ km s}^{-1} \text{ Mpc}^{-1}$ derived from the very nearby, low-redshift particle ($z = 0.013227$) that entered the Hubble flow comparatively later in the current (or more recent) epoch of cosmic expansion, moreover, just as before, the inverse of these particle-derived expansion rates (Equation (6)) directly yields the expansion onset time (t_E) for a given epoch, allowing exact epoch timing to be estimated, or when the particles entered the Hubble flow.

5. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

The interpretation of consecutive epochs of cosmic expansion, presented and tested in this study, provides a viable alternative to explain the observed curvature in the SNe Ia Hubble diagram; the phenomenological model tracks the observed curvature of the Pantheon+ SNe Ia Hubble diagram over the tested redshift range, producing results consistent with SNe Ia observations.

If the consecutive-expansion-epochs interpretation is valid, then the apparent transition of the Universe's expansion from past deceleration at high redshifts to recent acceleration at low redshifts (a single, continuous expansion) inferred from SNe Ia observations may be an artefact of blending consecutive epochs of cosmic expansion (multiple, consecutive expansions) on the same Hubble diagram.

Following the wording of Jha et al. (2007), I conclude, regardless of whether the interpretation of consecutive epochs of cosmic expansion, presented and tested in this study, makes us occupy a privileged position in an inhomogeneous Universe (Vishniac 2021, private communication) or puts us at the centre of an isotropic but inhomogeneous model (Davis 2022, private communication), the feature of “consecutive expansion epochs that preceded the current epoch of cosmic expansion” appears to be present in the Hubble flow SN sample over the tested redshift range.

6. FUTURE PROSPECTS

While this work presents and tests a phenomenological alternative by incorporating evaluation metrics – RMSE (error metric) and R^2 (goodness-of-fit metric) only, it shows that consecutive epochs of cosmic expansion can track the observed curvature of the SNe Ia Hubble diagram over the tested redshift range. Future work will incorporate more rigorous tests beyond the analysis presented here, additional cosmological probes (cosmic microwave background (CMB) and baryon acoustic oscillations (BAO)), even more high-redshift objects (quasars (QSOs) and gamma-ray bursts (GRBs)), and full-fledged General-Relativistic formulations to assess the model's overall viability. It will also be interesting to explore if this study has any implications for the Hubble tension (the discrepancy in the expansion rates of early Universe (a lower value) and late Universe (a higher value)), and, the impossible early galaxy problem (high-redshift galaxies appearing as bright, as evolved, and as massive as low-redshift galaxies).

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

I thank the researchers for making their data and software publicly available. I want to express my most sincere gratitude and appreciation to Professor Ethan Vishniac (2021) and Professor Tamara Davis (2022) for their valuable comments on an earlier version of this work. An even earlier version of this work was presented at the 26th Raman Memorial Conference held at Department of Physics, University of Pune, on 14th February 2020 [15].

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